

Advancing Science and Society: The Mission of Innovatio&Science Journal

Avanço da Ciência e da Sociedade: A Missão da Revista Innovatio&Science

EDITORIAL

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Abstract

Innovatio&Science Journal, as a multidisciplinary scientific journal, is committed to advancing academic excellence, innovation, and social impact. By implementing rigorous double-blind peer review standards and adopting an open access policy, the journal ensures the immediate dissemination of research findings. Covering critical areas such as Health, Biotechnology, Engineering, Technology, and Environment, the journal promotes interdisciplinary collaboration to address the urgent challenges of our times. With an unwavering commitment to ethical practices and a global reach, the journal aims to influence public policy and advance scientific knowledge.

Resumo

O Innovatio&Science Journal, como periódico científico multidisciplinar está comprometido em aprimorar a excelência acadêmica, a inovação e o impacto social. Ao implementar padrões rigorosos de revisão, por pares duplo-cego, e adotar uma política de acesso aberto, o periódico garante a disseminação imediata de descobertas de pesquisa. Abrangendo áreas críticas Saúde, Biotecnologia, Engenharia, Tecnologia e Meio Ambiente o periódico promove a colaboração interdisciplinar para enfrentar os desafios urgentes de nossos tempos. Com um compromisso inabalável com práticas éticas e alcance global, o periódico visa influenciar políticas públicas e promover o conhecimento científico.

Keywords: multidisciplinary, academic excellence, open access, peer review, innovation, social impact, interdisciplinary collaboration.

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PhD in Biotechnology from the Federal University of Piauí - Parnaíba Campus (2019) and a graduate in Biological Sciences from the same institution (2016), she has extensive experience in the areas of General Biology, Histology, Immunology, Pharmacology and Biotechnology. During her master's degree, she was part of the research group of the Laboratory of Pharmacology of Inflammation and Gastrointestinal Disorders (LAFIDG), where she conducted studies focused on inflammation and inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. Specialist in Active Methodologies and Innovative Practices from Fapesp/lesvap, in Immunology from the Metropolitan Faculty of São Paulo and in Microbiology from the Venda Nova do Imigrante Faculty (FAVENI). She was a professor in the medical course at the Faculdade Intitutoto Tocantinense Presidente Antônio Carlos (ITPAC) - Santa Inês, and currently has a teaching relationship with Faculdade Pitágoras, teaching in the medical courses on the Bacabal and Codó campuses. As a CNPq scholarship holder for his PhD in Pharmacology at the Federal University of Ceará (UFC), he worked at the Laboratory of Gastrointestinal Physio-Pharmacology Studies (LEFFAG), developing research on the role of hydrogen sulfide in gastroesophageal reflux disease. He worked as a Funadesp scholarship holder, investigating chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract with the research group Laboratório de inflamação e TGI bacabal, consolidating his academic career and contributing significantly to the advancement of knowledge in his area of specialization.

Kerolayne de Melo Nogueira
Editorial Committee Coordinator

Editorial

It is with great pleasure that we present the *Innovatio&Science Journal*, a multidisciplinary scientific journal that aims to be a platform for academic excellence, innovation and social impact. Our journal is more than a space for the dissemination of research; it is a commitment to the advancement of global knowledge and the construction of solutions for humanity's most complex challenges. We live in a time marked by significant transformations and global challenges in areas such as health, biotechnology, engineering, the environment and technology. In this scenario, science plays a vital role, being the pillar that supports innovations capable of transforming societies and promoting a sustainable future. IntellectusPress was born as a response to this need, offering a space for interdisciplinary collaboration for researchers, educators, students and professionals from various areas of knowledge.

Mission and Commitment to Science

Our mission is clear: to disseminate high-impact research, promote the democratization of knowledge and encourage scientific dialogue that transcends disciplinary and geographic boundaries. With this, we seek not only to share discoveries, but also to influence public policies, professional practices and social initiatives. Our commitment to excellent science is at the heart of our operations. To ensure the quality and relevance of each publication, we adopt a rigorous double-blind peer review process. This method ensures impartiality, confidentiality and a high scientific standard, allowing only original manuscripts of academic relevance and real impact to be published. IntellectusPress is guided by the highest ethical principles, in line with the guidelines of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) and international best editorial practices. We guarantee transparency throughout the editorial process, from submission to publication, promoting an environment of trust and respect among authors, reviewers and editors.

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Diversity of Formats and Broad Scope

Innovative Research Journal embraces scientific diversity, publishing a wide range of formats that reflect the complexity and richness of knowledge. We accept:

- Original articles: Unpublished reports of empirical or theoretical research.
- Review articles: Critical summaries that contribute to the advancement of the state of the art.
- Brief communications: Preliminary results that open up new possibilities for research.
- Reviews: Critical reflections on scientific works or advances in the field.
- Letters to the editor: Short discussions on emerging and relevant topics.

Our scope covers areas such as health, biotechnology, engineering, environment and technology, encouraging interdisciplinary dialogue and innovative approaches to contemporary issues.

Why Publish in Innovative Research Journal?

Choosing Innovative Research Journal as the destination for your scientific work means opting for:

- Scientific Rigor: We ensure a meticulous editorial process that prioritizes the quality, originality and relevance of each manuscript.
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- Agility: Our continuous flow policy accelerates the dissemination of knowledge, without compromising the rigor of the review process.
- Ethics and Transparency: We prioritize ethical principles at every stage, offering an editorial environment of trust and respect.
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We invite all researchers, professors and professionals to join us in the mission of transforming scientific discoveries into real impact. Whether by submitting your work, participating as reviewers or sharing our publications, you contribute to strengthening academic dialogue and expanding the horizons of science. At Innovative Research Journal, we believe that each published

research is not only a contribution to knowledge, but a concrete step towards a better future. Join us on this journey of innovation, excellence and transformation.